

SHORT COMMUNICATION OPEN ACCESS

Can the Movement of the Deep-Sea Bivalve *Acesta excavata* Lead to a Dynamic Habitat?

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ABSTRACT

Acesta excavata is one of the largest and ecologically relevant bivalves along continental margins and is often associated with cold-water coral assemblages of the upper bathyal zone. Like other habitat-forming species, *A. excavata* contributes to increasing the secondary substrata and provides opportunities for the colonization and feeding of other sessile and mobile organisms. Despite most of the bivalves producing byssus being thought to be sessile or sedentary throughout their adult life stages, some species are known to be able to displace. Here we investigated, in mesocosm conditions, the ability of this deep-sea species to move/displace and compared its mobility with that of other shallow-water species. We report here for the first time that *A. excavata* moves almost continuously, with a maximum speed of 6.5 cm day⁻¹ (maximum weekly displacement of ca 28 cm), with average speeds of approximately 0.3–1.3 cm per day. This speed is the highest value reported so far for byssus-attached bivalves (including *Mytilus* spp. and *Pictada imbricata radiata*). The movement of these bivalves, apparently due to the search for optimal feeding and substratum characteristics, can displace the habitat they create in response to changes in environmental and ecological conditions. These findings offer new opportunities for using this species in restoration protocols of deep-sea habitats and change our view of deep-sea hard bottoms from static to dynamic entities.

1 | Introduction

The deep sea represents the largest biome on Earth, accounting for more than 65% of the Earth's surface, encompassing more than 95% of the global biosphere (Danovaro et al. 2014). Deep-sea habitats provide key ecosystem goods and services (Danovaro et al. 2020) and hold a critical role in the functioning and buffering capability of the planet (Levin and Bris 2015), but the current knowledge of the biology of deep-sea species remains extremely limited (Snelgrove 1999).

Bivalves producing byssus both in shallow and deep ecosystems can generate aggregates that represent additional habitats characterized by biodiversity hotspots and rich in new substrata, protection, and food (Grabowski and Peterson 2007; Guillon et al. 2017; Hall-Spencer and Moore 2000; Johnson et al. 2013). They allow the settlement of the larvae of several sessile and mobile epifaunal species (Grabowski and Peterson 2007; Gutiérrez et al. 2003), increase habitat complexity through the creation of interstices between their valves and byssal threads, where mobile fauna can seek refuge (Gutiérrez et al. 2003), and entrap

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sediments and organic matter that offer additional opportunities for species colonization (Calcagno et al. 2012).

Investigating biological processes, such as growth, movement, physiology, and reproduction, often requires the combination of several approaches, including *ex situ* experimentation. The collection of live specimens and their *ex situ* maintenance could represent a challenge for deep-sea organisms (Orejas and Jiménez 2019), but several species adapt easily to captivity (Lartaud et al. 2014; Lunden et al. 2014; Orejas et al. 2011; Shillito et al. 2015). This is also the case of the bivalve *Acesta excavata* (Fabricius 1779) which was able to live and grow for years in controlled conditions (pers. observation). The long-term survival of this bivalve in mesocosms allows the collection of data on the ecology and behavior of this species that are difficult to gather in situ.

A. excavata is one of the most ecologically relevant deep-sea bivalves inhabiting hard bottoms typically at bathyal depths (Correa et al. 2005; Taviani et al. 2019; Zibrowius and Taviani 2005). It is often associated with the cold-water corals *Desmophyllum pertusum*, *Desmophyllum dianthus*, and *Madrepora oculata*, contributing to the formation of vulnerable habitats (Taviani et al. 2019; Zibrowius and Taviani 2005). Deep-sea cliffs are generally characterized by the presence of a high density of *A. excavata* and the oyster *Neopycnodonte zibrowii* (Johnson et al. 2013), which provide surface area for other benthic organisms. In particular, the shells of *A. excavata*, reaching a total length of around 20 cm, are often covered with serpulids, bryozoans, sponges, scleractinians, and oysters (Correa et al. 2005).

The biology, anatomy, and life strategies of bivalves largely depend on their life traits (Itchell Stanley 1968). For instance, the locomotion strategies divide bivalves into several ecological groups: (i) byssus-attached (i.e., bivalves producing byssal filaments for the anchoring to the substratum), (ii) borers producing holes in carbonate rocks (e.g., *Lithophaga lithophaga*) or wood materials; (iii) nesting (within a pre-existing cavity), (iv) cemented (e.g., oysters that are attached by secreted shell material to a hard substratum), (v) swimming (e.g., Limidae such as *Lima lima* free living with self-propulsion) (Itchell Stanley 1968). While some bivalves are known to swim (although for limited distances) and borers/cemented/nested are permanently sessile, byssus-attached bivalves can show some degrees of movement

(e.g., families Mytilidae and Margaritidae), although this is expected to occur almost exclusively during their early development (Martel and Chia 1991). Here we investigated the movement ecology of the deep-sea bivalve *A. excavata* to explore an unexplored aspect of the biology of this ecologically important habitat-forming species.

2 | Material and Methods

2.1 | Study Area and Sample Collection

To conduct this study, specimens of *A. excavata* were collected in Dohrn Canyon from a vertical cliff at about 400 m depth, corresponding to a biodiversity hotspot where *A. excavata* coexists with the corals *Madrepora oculata*, *Desmophyllum pertusum*, *Desmophyllum dianthus*, and the deep-sea oyster *Neopycnodonte zibrowii*.

Approximately ten bivalves (see a picture of their distribution in situ; Figure 1a) were collected (including both juveniles and adult specimens) by using a remotely operated vehicle (ROV) with a soft basket attached to the manipulator arm (Figure 1b). The number of bivalves collected was kept low to minimize the impact on the in situ population. The sampling device consisted of a cylindrical stainless-steel structure holding a 2 cm soft net, which allowed it to avoid any potential damage caused by the limited sensitivity of the arm itself. Once on board, the organisms were immediately placed in a thermally insulated container, connected to a Teco TK 1000 water chiller (Figure 1c) to maintain a constant temperature of 14.5°C, and transported to the aquarium facility for acclimatization.

2.2 | Mesocosm Setup and Maintenance

The mesocosm system consisted of a 700L Martini cargo pallet tank and a collection tank containing the filtration systems. The filtration system consisted of a 50- μ sock for mechanical filtration, 200L of biological media, and a UV sterilizer. A Teco TK 3000 chiller was installed to maintain a constant temperature. The water cycle was as follows: the pump drew water from the reservoir into the chiller and then through the UV sterilizer before reaching the main tank outlets. An overflow drain returned the water to the collection tank for mechanical and biological filtration. The

FIGURE 1 | Phases of the collection of the bivalve of *A. excavata*. Reported are: (a) a picture of *Acesta* in situ (Dohrn Canyon, Tyrrhenian Sea, Mediterranean); (b) ROV equipped with the collection basket; (c) refrigerated box for the transport of the specimens.

system received continuous water exchange for 10 h a day at a flow rate of 2 L per minute. Seawater was changed weekly and ensuring the supply directly from the sea. This Life Support System (LSS) allowed the highest standards of animal welfare to be achieved, whilst providing a dark environment that was easily accessible for feeding, cleaning, and monitoring operations. To provide vertical surfaces and attachment points for the organisms, a plastic box was placed in the center of the tank. Debris siphoning was carried out once a week in parallel with the monitoring of key water parameters. In situ temperature (14.5°C), oxygen (8 mg/L) and salinity (38 PSU) conditions were replicated in the controlled environment and measured three times a week.

Two adult bivalves of the same size class (10.8 ± 0.5 cm) were used for the experiment. Bivalves were fed daily with a broad-spectrum experimental diet (Table 1), including both cultured and prepared foods. The cultured component included microalgae (*Tetraselmis*), rotifers, and *Artemia salina* nauplii. The noncultured components included a 500- μ m filtered mixture of marine sauce (mixtures of mussels, shrimps and fish) and Shellfish Diet 1800 (prepared mixture of *Isochrysis* spp., *Pavlova* spp., *Tetraselmis* spp., *Thalassiosira weissflogii* and *Thalassiosira pseudonana*).

TABLE 1 | Composition of the experimental diet administered to *A. excavata* individuals throughout the maintenance period.

Food	Type	Quantity (ml)	[C] (ind/ml*—cell/ml**)
<i>Tetraselmis suecica</i>	Cultured	500	$1-2 \times 10^{6**}$
<i>Brachionus plicatilis</i>	Cultured	500	20*
<i>Artemia salina</i> (nauplii)	Cultured	500	10*
Mix marine flesh	Prepared	500	ND
Shellfish Diet 1800	Prepared	10	ND

Note: The asterisks referred to the units of measurement related to each food. (*) stands for ind/ml and (**) stands for cell/ml.

The experiment lasted approximately 7 months (225 days) from September 2020 to April 2021, and data on bivalve movements were collected randomly with a ca. weekly frequency.

2.3 | Observations and Analysis of Bivalve Movements

The individuals of *A. excavata* were carefully placed on the bottom of the aquarium on 1 September 2020. The first detectable movements were observed after one week, followed by weekly monitoring for 6 months, from September 2020 to April 2021. HD images of the moving bivalves were collected using a Nikon COOLPIX AW130 digital camera and a ruler to set the scale.

The size and position of the serpulid worms occurring on the right valves were used to identify each specimen (Figure 2). Images were processed using ImageJ to track displacement and direction of movement using the umbo as a reference point; graphical analyses were performed using Prism Graph Pad 8.

3 | Results

Visual observations indicate that in *A. excavata* the byssus can be secreted, utilized, and discarded in a sequential process to actively pull the bivalve and determine its displacement from one substratum to another. Both horizontal, vertical, and rotational displacements were observed (see Additional file 1). All specimens showed a recurrent pattern for both vertical and horizontal displacement which is reported as follows: (i) the foot extends from the anterior side and directs the deposition of a new byssus; (ii) the outer part of the byssus, consisting of a few filaments (usually five), anchors the animal to the substratum; (iii) the newly deposited byssus is used to pull the shell, while the old byssus remains anchored and is stretched in the direction of movement; and finally (iv) the old byssus is detached and left behind (Figure 3).

Once the specimens were left on the bottom of the tank, they began to move in the horizontal plane until they encountered a vertical surface. Individuals showed two alternative approaches: (i) wall climbing and continuous movement; (ii) short distance movement to then settle for a longer time in a suitable area (e.g., the corner of a plastic box over a vertical surface).

FIGURE 2 | Specimens of *A. excavata* used in this study and their distinguishing features (serpulid worm remains on the right valves).

Daily measurements provided evidence also of the rotational ability: *A. excavata* can rotate for more than 180° in approximately 4 h using exclusively its foot (Figure 4).

During the entire experimental period, the most dynamic specimen covered a total distance of 230 cm with an average speed of 1.3 cm per day⁻¹. The least dynamic specimen moved for a total of 76 cm, with an average speed of 0.3 cm per day⁻¹. Considering net displacements, the speed was 1.8 ± 1.5 cm per day⁻¹ and 1.1 ± 1.0 cm per day⁻¹ for the two specimens, respectively. The maximum velocity was recorded during horizontal displacements with 6.5 cm per day⁻¹ (Figure 5).

4 | Discussion

Data reported in this study document, for the first time, that the adults of the large bivalve *A. excavata* actively move by using their byssal threads, thus revealing that the byssus of this

bivalve is not used only as a tool to remain firmly attached to the substratum. Our observations also provided evidence of the mechanism through which the byssus is used: (i) the byssus is secreted and attached to various parts of the substratum, then part of the byssus is discarded, and (ii) the animal actively pulls through some attached filaments allowing its movements.

Available information indicates that the oyster *Pinctada imbricata radiata* (family Margaritidae) can move with a maximum displacement of 3.1 cm day⁻¹ (Giraldes et al. 2019), and similar values were reported for adult mussels (*Mytilus* spp.) (Schneider et al. 2005). In addition, laboratory experiments have shown that mussels tend to orient to intercept the prevailing water flow, thereby exposing a smaller surface area and reducing the hydrodynamic force (Zardi et al. 2006).

The movements of *A. excavata* are almost continuous and, together with the ability to rotate on the substratum using the foot, allow this bivalve to find the best attachment position. In

FIGURE 3 | The sequence of displacement of *A. excavata* highlights the deposition of new byssus filaments (red lines) and the stretching of old filaments (white lines) in the direction of movement.

FIGURE 4 | Photographic sequence of the rotation of the *A. excavata* over the substratum carried out using its foot.

FIGURE 5 | Range of observed displacement (a) and speed (b) of *A. excavata* specimens during the monitoring period.

fact, due to the high spatial heterogeneity of hard substrata and surrounding water flows, even small-scale displacements can result in relevant changes in the environmental characteristics to which the bivalves are exposed. Such changes may play an important role in offering better feeding and growth conditions, thus ultimately regulating population fitness. Although the specific factors triggering the movement in *A. excavata* remain unknown, visual observations carried out in mesocosm conditions indicate that the most likely factor triggering the bivalve displacement is represented by the search for optimal water flow conditions associated with adequate protection (pers. observ.).

It is known that bivalves in general have a wide range of sensory structures, including simple and complex organs (Audino et al. 2015; Haszprunar 1985), but little information is currently available on the sensory system of *A. excavata* and its perception of environmental stimuli (Järnegren and Altin 2006). We know that this bivalve possesses structures along the mantle margin that act as mechanoreceptors, chemoreceptors, or photoreceptors (Audino et al. 2015). *Acesta*, like other members of the Limidae family, shows long tentacles and eyes on the mantle margin (Järnegren and Altin 2006). In the pectinid bivalve *Limaria hians*, these tentacles are thought to contain structures acting as multidirectional mechanoreceptors, vibration receptors, and/or chemoreceptors (Owen et al. 1997).

Another issue to consider is the fact that all measures are obtained in controlled conditions (mesocosms), which, although recreates most of the ambient conditions, do not reflect perfectly the in situ conditions (e.g., pressure). Therefore, we assume that the data collected in captivity might reflect those observed in natural conditions, which, of course, might vary from those observed experimentally. Nonetheless, the result obtained offers evidence of the speed and range of displacement that is possible for this bivalve. Moreover, these measurements allow a comparison to be carried out with other species whose movements were observed in similar controlled conditions.

During the ca. 7 months of the experiment, the longest track of a single bivalve was ca. 2.3 m with an average speed of ca.

1.0 cm day⁻¹. The maximum speed (6.5 cm day⁻¹) was observed during horizontal displacements (see supplementary information). These values are higher than any others reported so far, including those measured for common mussels at shallow depths (<25 cm month⁻¹) (Nicastro et al. 2008; Schneider et al. 2005; Zardi et al. 2006). Although the data available for other bivalve species are too limited to draw general conclusions, it might be hypothesized that bivalves in the deep sea might require important movements to increase their fitness to local conditions.

The dominant direction of the movements of the bivalve *A. excavata* once released on the bottom of the mesocosm was vertical, thus leading to the hypothesis that the bivalve was in search of vertical substrata offering the optimal distance from the bottom to intercept the strongest currents. A decrease in speed and displacement was observed after the bivalve reached a position on a vertical wall, yet small movements and rotatory adjustments were performed even after vertical walls, suggesting a continuous search of the optimal water flow.

The active displacement capacity of byssus-attached species has been so far largely overlooked. The present study on *A. excavata* could provide important insights for understanding the functional responses of this species to abiotic and biotic drivers. This information can also be useful for the attempts to restore deep-sea habitats created by *A. excavata* or cold-water coral habitats with which this bivalve can cooperate as observed for other bivalves in vegetated habitats (Gagnon et al. 2020). These findings also indicate that we should revise our view of deep-sea hard bottoms and related megafaunal habitats as static entities, as those created by this bivalve could displace significantly over time.

Author Contributions

Danovaro R. and Sacco D. planned the experiments. Sacco D., Cardone F. and Canese S. P. collected the organism; Sacco D. and Cardone F. arranged the experiments in the tanks; Sacco D. performed the experiment and photographic data collection; Sacco D. and Cardinale P. analyzed the data and wrote the manuscript. All authors edited the manuscript. Danovaro R. reviewed the manuscript.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

All data generated or analyzed during this study are included in this published article [and its supplementary information files].

References

- Audino, J. A., J. E. A. R. Marian, A. Wanninger, and S. G. B. C. Lopes. 2015. “Anatomy of the Pallial Tentacular Organs of the Scallop *Nodipecten nodosus* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Bivalvia: Pectinidae).” *Zoologischer Anzeiger* 258: 39–46.
- Calcagno, J. A., J. N. Curelovich, V. M. Fernandez, S. Thatje, and G. A. Lovrich. 2012. “Effects of Physical Disturbance on a Sub-Antarctic Middle Intertidal Bivalve Assemblage.” *Marine Biology Research* 8, no. 10: 937–953. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17451000.2012.702911>.
- Correa, M. L., A. Freiwald, J. Hall-Spencer, and M. Taviani. 2005. “Distribution and Habitats of *Acesta excavata* (Bivalvia: Limidae) With New Data on Its Shell Ultrastructure.” In *Cold-Water Corals and Ecosystems*, 173–205. Springer.
- Danovaro, R., E. Fanelli, J. Aguzzi, et al. 2020. “Ecological Variables for Developing a Global Deep-Ocean Monitoring and Conservation Strategy.” *Nature Ecology & Evolution* 4: 181–192.
- Danovaro, R., P. V. R. Snelgrove, and P. Tyler. 2014. “Challenging the Paradigms of Deep-Sea Ecology.” *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 29: 465–475.
- Gagnon, K., E. Rinde, E. G. T. Bengil, et al. 2020. “Facilitating Foundation Species: The Potential for Plant–Bivalve Interactions to Improve Habitat Restoration Success.” *Journal of Applied Ecology* 57: 1161–1179.
- Giraldes, B. W., A. Leitão, and D. Smyth. 2019. “The Benthic Sea-Silk-Thread Displacement of a Sessile Bivalve, *Pinctada imbricata radiata* (Leach, 1819) in the Arabian-Persian Gulf.” *PLoS One* 14: e0215865.
- Grabowski, J. H., and C. H. Peterson. 2007. “Restoring Oyster Reefs to Recover Ecosystem Services.” In *Theoretical Ecology Series*, 281–298. Elsevier.
- Guillon, E., L. Menot, C. Decker, E. Krylova, and K. Olu. 2017. “The Vesicomid Bivalve Habitat at Cold Seeps Supports Heterogeneous and Dynamic Macrofaunal Assemblages.” *Deep Sea Research Part I: Oceanographic Research Papers* 120: 1–13.
- Gutiérrez, J. L., C. G. Jones, D. L. Strayer, and O. O. Iribarne. 2003. “Mollusks as Ecosystem Engineers: The Role of Shell Production in Aquatic Habitats.” *Oikos* 101, no. 1: 79–90. <https://doi.org/10.1034/j.1600-0706.2003.12322.x>.
- Hall-Spencer, J. M., and P. G. Moore. 2000. “*Limaria hians* (Mollusca: Limacea): A Neglected Reef-Forming Keystone Species.” *Aquatic Conservation* 10: 267–277.
- Haszprunar, G. 1985. “The Fine Structure of the Abdominal Sense Organs of Pteriomorpha (Mollusca, Bivalvia).” *Journal of Molluscan Studies* 51: 315–319.
- Itchell Stanley, S. M. 1968. *Relation of Shell Form to Life Habits in the Bivalvia (Mollusca)*. Vol. 125. Geological Society of America. <https://doi.org/10.1130/MEM125>.
- Järnegren, J., and D. Altin. 2006. “Filtration and Respiration of the Deep Living Bivalve *Acesta excavata* (J.C. Fabricius, 1779) (Bivalvia; Limidae).” *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 334: 122–129.
- Johnson, M. P., M. White, A. Wilson, et al. 2013. “A Vertical Wall Dominated by *Acesta excavata* and *Neopycnodonte zibrowii*, Part of an Undersampled Group of Deep-Sea Habitats.” *PLoS One* 8, no. 11: e79917. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0079917>.
- Lartaud, F., S. Pareige, M. de Rafelis, et al. 2014. “Temporal Changes in the Growth of Two Mediterranean Cold-Water Coral Species, In Situ and in Aquaria.” *Deep-Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography* 99: 64–70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dsr2.2013.06.024>.
- Levin, L. A., and N. L. Bris. 2015. “The Deep Ocean Under Climate Change.” *Science* 350, no. 6262: 766–768.
- Lunden, J. J., J. M. Turner, C. G. McNicholl, C. K. Glynn, and E. E. Cordes. 2014. “Design, Development, and Implementation of Recirculating Aquaria for Maintenance and Experimentation of Deep-Sea Corals and Associated Fauna.” *Limnology and Oceanography: Methods* 12: 363–372.
- Martel, A., and F. Chia. 1991. “Drifting and Dispersal of Small Bivalves and Gastropods with Direct Development.” *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 150: 131–147. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-0981\(91\)90111-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-0981(91)90111-9).
- Nicastro, K. R., G. I. Zardi, and C. D. McQuaid. 2008. “Movement Behaviour and Mortality in Invasive and Indigenous Mussels: Resilience and Resistance Strategies at Different Spatial Scales.” *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 372: 119–126.
- Orejas, C., C. Ferrier-Pagès, S. Reynaud, et al. 2011. “Long-Term Growth Rates of Four Mediterranean Cold-Water Coral Species Maintained in Aquaria.” *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 429: 57–65.
- Orejas, C., and C. Jiménez (Eds.). 2019. *Mediterranean Cold-Water Corals: Past, Present and Future: Understanding the Deep-Sea Realms of Coral*. Vol. 9. Springer.
- Owen, G., J. M. McCrae, and M. Yonge. 1997. “Sensory Cell/Gland Cell Complexes Associated With the Pallial Tentacles of the Bivalve *Lima hians* (Gmelin), With a Note on Specialized Cilia on the Pallial Curtains.” *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London B, Biological Sciences* 287: 45–62.
- Schneider, K. R., D. S. Wetthey, B. S. T. Helmuth, and T. J. Hilbish. 2005. “Implications of Movement Behavior on Mussel Dislodgement: Exogenous Selection in a *Mytilus* spp. Hybrid Zone.” *Marine Biology* 146: 333–343.
- Shillito, B., J. Ravoux, J. Sarrazin, M. Zbinden, P. M. Sarradin, and D. Barthelemy. 2015. “Long-Term Maintenance and Public Exhibition of Deep-Sea Hydrothermal Fauna: The AbyssBox Project.” *Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography* 121: 137–145.
- Snelgrove, P. V. R. 1999. “Getting to the Bottom of Marine Biodiversity: Sedimentary Habitats Ocean Bottoms Are the Most Widespread Habitat on Earth and Support High Biodiversity and Key Ecosystem Services.” *BioScience* 49, no. 2: 129–138. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1313538>.
- Taviani, M., L. Angeletti, F. Cardone, P. Montagna, and R. Danovaro. 2019. “A Unique and Threatened Deep Water Coral-Bivalve Biotope New to the Mediterranean Sea Offshore the Naples Megalopolis.” *Scientific Reports* 9: 3411.

Zardi, G. I., K. R. Nicastro, C. D. McQuaid, M. Rius, and F. Porri. 2006. "Hydrodynamic Stress and Habitat Partitioning Between Indigenous (*Perna perna*) and Invasive (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*) Mussels: Constraints of an Evolutionary Strategy." *Marine Biology* 150: 79–88.

Zibrowius, H., and M. Taviani. 2005. "Remarkable Sessile Fauna Associated With Deep Coral and Other Calcareous Substrates in the Strait of Sicily, Mediterranean Sea." In *Cold-Water Corals and Ecosystems*, 807–819. Springer.

Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.